

Proof for Twin Prime Conjecture

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The question about Twin Primes is pretty clear:

"Twin primes are prime numbers that differ by 2. Are there infinitely many twin primes?"

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I. Introduction

If any number group containing "n" consecutive and odd non-prime numbers is selected among the infinite number groups, this group must be between 2 prime numbers according to this condition. For n=4, choose a group of numbers as follows, consisting of 4 consecutive odd numbers, n_1, n_2, n_3 and n_4 , which are between 2 prime numbers such as p_1 and p_2 .

$p_1 \quad n_1 \quad n_2 \quad n_3 \quad n_4 \quad p_2$

II. Solution

Theorem *At least one of these non-prime consecutive odd numbers of "n" must be an odd multiple of 3; because the distribution of odd multiples of 3 in the set of odd numbers depends on the function $f(x)=6x+3$, and therefore in the set of odd numbers there are always 2 consecutive odd numbers between every two consecutive odd multiples of 3.*

$n_0 \quad n_x \quad p_1 \quad n_1 \quad n_2 \quad n_3 \quad n_4 \quad p_2 \quad n_y \quad n_5$

- If the odd number n_2 is considered an odd multiple of 3, the prime number p_2 must be the next consecutive odd multiple of 3.
Since p_2 is a prime number, this is only possible if it falls on a non-prime number in a group such as $n=5$.
For $n=4$, different groups must be formed.
- If the odd number n_3 is considered an odd multiple of 3, then the prime number p_1 must be the previous consecutive odd multiple of 3.
Since p_1 is a prime number, this is only possible if it falls on a non-prime number in a group such as $n=5$.
For $n=4$, different groups must be formed.
- If the odd number n_1 is considered an odd multiple of 3, the odd number n_4 must be the next consecutive odd multiple of 3.
Also, the odd number n_5 must be the second consecutive odd multiple of 3 immediately after the odd number n_4 , and the odd number n_0 must be the previous odd multiple of 3 before the odd number n_1 .
- If the odd number n_4 is considered an odd multiple of 3, the odd number n_5 must be the next consecutive odd multiple of 3.
Also, for this acceptance, the odd numbers n_0 and n_1 must be previous consecutive odd multiples of 3; so *"The odd numbers n_1 and n_4 are the best choice to be odd multiples of 3."*

III. Result

The odd number n_5 can be followed by an infinite number of consecutive odd numbers "n"; therefore, for any value of "n" after the group $n = 4$, the number of elements of an odd set of numbers "n" is unimportant; but the odd number n_y is always prime or not, which is important. With this information, the $n_y = n_5 - 2 = (6x + 3) - 2$ equation forms the (1) equation.

$$n_y = 6x + 1 \tag{1}$$

So it can be said for n_y ;

- I. n_y out of (1) with the condition $x \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \wedge x > 0$ can never be just a prime or a non-prime number.
- II. It is not prime over (1) for an "x" value that does this; but it is prime for odd numbers formed between two numbers n_y and n_{y+1} which are the result of two consecutive numbers x and $x + 1$.
- III. After all, when $n_y = p_3$ it is a group of twin primes between odd numbers n_4 and n_5 ; therefore twin primes are "infinite" even for the groups which have the same number of elements and different numbers that these groups can be written even for only a single value "n".

Result *"Twin primes are prime numbers that differ by 2, and there are an infinite number of twin primes."*

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IV. Appendix

Actually, I felt the need to make 2 additional proofs about the construction of this proof, although it was not necessary because it was easy to animate.

- a. The first of these is about the existence of n groups. Topics related to these groups are as follows.
 - Existence of an infinite set of numbers "containing n odd non-prime numbers between 2 prime numbers" for a positive and identical odd integer n .
 - Whether there are infinite "groups of n " formed for varying n values.
- b. The other is about the (1) equality. The issues related to this equality are as follows.
 - Whether it returns a prime number only.
 - Whether returns non-prime results only.

a. The Groups

I.

Forexample, for the group $n = 5$, let's take consecutive multiples of 3, 5, 7, 9, and 11, although any odd numbers can be used. Since a is an odd number, any multiple of odd numbers is $a(2x + 1)$ for the required x ; well

- $(6x_1 + 3) + 2 = 10x_2 + 5$
it becomes $x_1 = 5x$
- $(6x_1 + 3) + 4 = 14x_3 + 7$
it becomes $x_1 = 7x$
- $(6x_1 + 3) + 6 = 18x_4 + 9$
it becomes $x_1 = 9x$
- $(6x_1 + 3) + 8 = 22x_5 + 11$
it becomes $x_1 = 11x$

The results of $6x_1 + 3$, which are odd multiples of 3, become $30x + 3$, $42x + 3$, $54x + 3$ and $66x + 3$ for the specified values of x_1 . If these are made equal to each other,

$$(11 \cdot 9 \cdot 7 \cdot 5 \cdot x) = u$$

and if the first number of the group is a multiple of 3, the consecutive multiples of the group numbers are $6u + 3$, $6u + 5$, $6u + 7$, $6u + 9$ and $6u + 11$, respectively. For more distinct consecutive odd multiples, we can increase the number of numbers used in a group in the same way infinitely.

II.

A group as above does not always have to be between 2 primes; because the numbers that make up the group are also important. This also does not mean that groups between 2 primes are not infinite. Let's talk about the infinity of groups.

In fact, its proof requires no mathematical operations; because as long as the primes are not consecutive, there will be infinitely different groups for varying n values.

Result *"The function $f(x) = 6x + 1$ sequentially returns for each value of x not only a single non-prime number, consecutive or not."*

Since all odd non-prime numbers are $(2x+1)(2y+1)$ for every integer value of x and y numbers

$$(2x + 1)(2y + 1) = 1$$

In an equation such as, x and y , which only take certain values, do not occur, like in a function with 1 unknown from the 1st degree. This is exactly a hyperbola; therefore, the distribution of prime and non-prime odd numbers does not depend on consecutive rules between any two consecutive primes.

b. The Function

If the function $f(x) = 6x + 1$ returns only non-prime numbers and *consecutive* all odd numbers

$$(2x + 1)(2y + 1) = 6z + 1$$

equality must be satisfied for each x and y value, respectively; because odd non-prime numbers are odd multiples of prime and odd non-prime numbers.

Having a z -value for every x and y -value means that odd non-prime numbers have something in common with all of them. Otherwise, it can sometimes give a prime. For this, with the equation $m = (2x + 1)(2y + 1)$

$$\frac{m - 1}{2} = 3n$$

equation is analyzed. Equality means that any number that is equal to $6n + 1$ must be divisible by 3 at the end of the operation; in that case

$$2(6a + 3) + 1 = 6b + 3$$

equality must be achieved. If edited

$$b - 2a = \frac{2}{3}$$

This means that; when the even number $m - 1$ is divisible by 2, the odd number formed must be a multiple of 3, and the odd number before or after the even number $m - 1$ can never be a number divisible by 3. $m - 1$ is always between two consecutive odd multiples of 3; *then numbers that are multiples of 3 of all other odd numbers* cannot be between two consecutive odd multiples of 3, so there must be primes in between.

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